

Mapping Research Topics on Operational Risk in The Sharia and Conventional Financial Industry: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review

Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi
Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang
wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract

The primary aim of this study is to examine the advancement and growth of research on operational hazards in the Islamic and Conventional Financial Industry from 2002 to 2022. The investigators conducted a comprehensive search for pertinent articles in domestic and international journals listed by Google Scholar, Sinta, and Scopus using the Perish/Harzing application with the term "Operational Risk". This procedure resulted in a total of 348 research articles, which were then analyzed descriptively through a review of literature using the VOSviewer application. The findings indicated a significant rise in the number of publications on operational hazard each year. The VOSviewer analysis recognized 9 distinct clusters of research linked to operational hazards. Furthermore, the literature review revealed 11 primary themes that are closely associated with operational hazard in both Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

Keywords: Operational Risk, Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Sharia and Conventional Financial Industry.

Introduction

Risk management in the Financial Industry has developed in line with the overall progress of the financial industry. In recent years, the Financial Industry has realized the importance of risk management in maintaining business stability and sustainability (Akbar. C et al., 2020) . Risks associated with the financial sector must be identified and managed by anticipating potential future problems, rather than simply responding to risks after they arise (Aprilia et al., 2022) . One of the risks in the financial sector is operational risk. Operational risk management includes a process by which risks are identified, assessed, monitored and continuously monitored to ensure the bank's stability and protect its reputation (Akbar. C et al., 2022) .

In previous research, in the activities carried out by the Islamic banking financial industry, there will definitely be a relationship with operational risk. If the institution succeeds in managing operational risks (Hassanein, 2021) . Currently, operational risks are increasingly being discovered due to several cases in the Financial Industry. The identification process begins with understanding the business processes in the main business operations through mapping. After that, factors that can cause operational risks must be discovered (Kunz, 2021) . Through

good control and management of operational processes, operational risks can be reduced and controlled effectively. Banks must allocate part of their capital to overcome operational risks (Kulinska-Sadtocha, 2022) . The operating ratio must be within 8% of the capital adequacy ratio (CAR) using the BIA method. The BIA method is too simple and only provides a top-down view, so it does not take into account other important factors (Cristea, 2021) .

This research aims to map research topics related to operational risk in the Islamic and conventional financial industry. This task is accomplished in two ways: (1) *VOSviewer bibliometric method*; and (2) Literature review is used to analyze, identify and evaluate articles related to operational risk in indexed and internationally accredited national journals.

Literature Review

Operational risk is the risk associated with failure to carry out banking operational activities, such as internal errors, technical failures, or failure to carry out existing procedures. Operational risks can result in financial, reputational losses, or even failure to meet regulatory obligations. This is to identify and manage operational risks to ensure business continuity and minimize potential losses. The main objective of Operational Risk Management is to ensure the continuity of the bank's business and minimize potential losses. This is done by identifying and managing operational risks that may occur in bank operational activities (Oyewo, 2022) .

Bibliometric research is a statistical and computer method for evaluating the production, citation, and dissemination of information in scientific literature (Dubyna et al., 2022) . *VOSviewer* is a bibliometric data visualization and scientific publication analysis software. Its main function is to show analysis of data references, quotes, and accompanying words in easy-to-understand charts and graphs (van Eck NJ, 2022) .

A research literature review is the process of identifying, evaluating, and synthesizing the results of previous research on a particular topic. Literature review studies are usually part of a larger research process where the researcher wishes to ensure an understanding of the existing research environment and avoid duplication of previous research results. Literature search research can also help researchers identify themes and gaps in existing literature, generate hypotheses, and understand specific areas of research. When researching literature, researchers can use various public research databases (El-Halaby et al., 2021) .

Methodology

This study uses a combination technique, namely a mixed technique. Quantitative methods are used in bibliometric research and qualitative methods are used in literary research. The aim of this research is to explore operational risk. The data used in this research is secondary data obtained from scientific journal articles about operational risks in the Islamic and conventional financial sectors. To collect data, researchers used *Perish/Harzing* to search for national and international journals

indexed by *Google Scholar*, *Sprott*, and *Scopus*. The data analysis tool used in this research is *Microsoft Excel software*, *Mendeley Desktop*, and *VOSviewer*.

The data collection process involves the following steps: (1) Search for journals based on word categories in the title using the keyword "operational risk" from 2002 to 2022 using *Perish/Harzing*. (2) Collect journal title data in *Microsoft Excel* and identify possible duplications. (3) Download RIS (*Research Information Systems*) and PDF (*Portable files Document Format*) from all journals that are data sources. (4) Import the RIS file into the *Mendeley desktop program*.

The data analysis steps are as follows: (1) Organizing RIS data files by year, author, and publisher using *Mendeley Desktop*. (2) Create visualizations of bibliometric networks and scientific publication trends using *VOSviewer software* (similarity visualization) based on the number of clusters and their elements. (3) Analyze the research topic based on a literature review related to previous research. By using this analytical method, this research can provide a clear picture of operational risks in the Islamic and conventional financial sectors (Budianto & Dewi, 2022).

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Operational Risk in the Sharia and Conventional Financial Industry

Perish/Harzing application data collection from 2002 to 2022, there are 348 international and national journals. There are 186 international journals indexed by *Scopus*, 162 international and national journals indexed by *Sinta* related to operational risk studies.

Table 1. Journal publication data regarding Operational Risk by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2002	3	2010	14	2017	23
2003	2	2011	19	2018	24
2005	2	2012	17	2019	33
2006	6	2013	15	2020	24
2007	6	2014	9	2021	46
2008	12	2015	19	2022	52
2009	11	2016	11		

Source: Processed data, *Microsoft Excel* 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Operational Risk in the Sharia and Conventional Financial Industry

The results are as follows:

- Cluster 8, 2 topic items, namely: *capital structure, insurance company.*
- Cluster 9, 2 topic items, namely: *Chinese commercial banking, operational risk.*

Literature Review Study regarding Operational Risk

There are 2 findings in the research topic regarding credit risk at a glance, namely:

First, the definition of operational risk. Operational Risk is a risk related to failure in carrying out banking operational activities, such as internal errors, technical failures, or failure to carry out existing procedures. Operational risks can result in financial, reputational losses, or even failure to meet regulatory obligations.

Second, the aim of operational risk management in banking is to minimize potential losses so that banks can continue to operate efficiently and effectively. This is done by identifying, evaluating and controlling operational risks through the implementation of effective and continuous risk management processes and procedures.

Literature Review Study regarding Operational Risk Supervision

There are 4 findings in research topics around operational risk monitoring, namely:

First, the authority and responsibility of the Board of Commissioners is to ensure that the Bank has good systems and processes to identify, manage and manage operational risks. The primary authority of the Council. It contains: (1) The Supervisory Board must ensure that the bank has principles and procedures. (2) The Supervisory Board ensures that the bank's operational risk management system runs well. (3) The Supervisory Board must ensure that the bank has sufficient resources to manage and control operational risks. and (4) The Board of Directors must ensure that the bank has an effective reporting and communication system to monitor and control operational risks.

Second, the authority and responsibilities of the Board of Directors, namely: (1) The Board of Directors must ensure that the bank has long-term strategies and goals that can overcome operational risks; (2) The Board of Directors must ensure that the bank has effective systems and procedures to manage and control operational risks; (3) The Board of Directors must ensure that the bank has a good internal control system to ensure that operational activities are carried out correctly and efficiently; (4) The Board of Directors must establish clear risk management objectives and ensure that these objectives are achieved; (5) The Board of Directors needs to ensure that the bank's operational risk management system functions well and meets applicable standards.

Third, Human Resources, namely:

- (1) Banks must have ethics that are applied at every level of the organization. Ethics includes moral and professional principles that must be applied at every level of the organization, including management, officers, and employees. Good ethics in operational risk will help banks ensure that operational activities are carried

out correctly and transparently, thereby minimizing operational risk. Ethics will also help banks build good relationships with customers, investors and other related parties.

- (2) Banks must provide consequential penalties to employees and officials who are proven to have committed violations and irregularities. Consistent sanctions will also help maintain the bank's integrity and reputation, and ensure that bank employees and officials understand how important ethics and professionalism are in dealing with operational risks. However, sanctions must also be applied fairly and proportionally. Banks must ensure that any sanctions action is based on clear and objective evidence, and considers all relevant factors, such as the severity of the violation and the circumstances involved.

Fourth, Operational Risk Management Organization.

Literature Review Study regarding Strategy, Risk Levels and Operational Risk Limits

First, Operational risk management strategy. The findings in this research topic are that the development of Operational Risk Management strategies in banking must be guided by applicable regulations, so that banks must form a Risk Management Work Unit.

Second, the level of risk to be taken (*risk appetite*) and risk tolerance (*risk tolerance*). The findings in this research topic are that the risks to be taken and risk tolerance will be based on applicable rules and regulations. The Bank will assess and measure existing operational risks, prioritize risks that need to be controlled and create policies to manage these risks. Operational risk tolerance is determined based on the level of risk that the bank can accept, taking into account factors such as the impact and likelihood of each risk. Once risks are identified and risk tolerance is determined, the bank will develop strategies to manage and reduce operational risks, such as by implementing appropriate procedures and internal controls, monitoring risks periodically, and taking corrective action if necessary.

Third, limits. The findings in this research topic are that setting limits is the process of limiting the amount of risk that a bank is allowed to take. In this case, limits for Operational Risk can be determined based on risk analysis, assessment of risk sources, as well as consideration of banking business objectives and strategies.

Literature Review Study regarding Operational Risk Policies and Procedures

There are 7 findings in research topics regarding operational risk policies and procedures in banking, namely:

First, banks must have an Operational Risk Management (MRO) policy to ensure that they can manage operational risks that may occur in their operational activities. The MRO policy must include the procedures and actions that will be taken to identify, evaluate and control operational risks. This policy must be applied consistently and continuously across

the bank and created taking into account factors such as business processes, technology systems and the regulatory environment.

Second, banks must also have procedures that are derivative of this policy, including general controls and specific controls.

Third, banks must have *Business Continuity Management (BCM)* to ensure that they can maintain their business operations during and after a disaster or emergency. BCM is an integrated and comprehensive process for managing risks that affect business operations and ensuring that banks can maintain their business continuity.

Fourth, in order to minimize internal operational risks, banks can do the following things: (1) Banks can identify complex internal processes and introduce streamlining and simplification methodologies to simplify and speed up these processes; (2) Banks can strengthen internal control; (3) Banks can utilize information systems and technology to simplify and speed up internal processes. Information systems and technology can help banks to manage and monitor internal processes effectively; (4) Banks can conduct staff training and certification; and (5) Banks can carry out regular monitoring and evaluation of internal processes.

Fifth, to reduce operational risks originating from customers and potential customers, the Risk Management Policy must include procedures for implementing *Customer Due Diligence (CDD)* or *Enhanced Due Diligence (EDD)* to ensure that banks carry out adequate checks and verification of their customers. CDD and EDD are processes used to ensure that banks understand customer profiles and the risks associated with those customers before starting a business relationship with them.

Sixth, in order to minimize Operational Risk originating from systems and infrastructure, Banks must have: (1) Implementation of Technology Security Standards; (2) Periodic *Monitoring and Testing*; (3) Documentation and *Recovery Procedures*; (4) Access control; and (5) Collaboration with vendors.

Seventh, to avoid operational risks originating from outside, banks must carry out: (1) *Monitoring* and evaluating the external environment; (2) Collaboration with business partners; (3) Credit risk management; (4) Portfolio diversification; (5) Determination of limits and Internal Control.

Literature Review Study regarding the Identification and Measurement of Operational Risk

There are 4 findings in the research topic surrounding the identification and measurement of operational risk in banking, namely:

First, identifying and measuring parameters that influence operational risk is important for banks. This helps them understand and assess the level of risk they face. The process of identifying and measuring operational risks involves the following steps: (1) Identifying risk sources; (2) Risk level assessment; (3) Determination of risk categories; (4) Determination of risk measurement parameters; and (5) *Monitoring* and evaluation.

Second, banks must have a comprehensive and up-to-date database for their operational risk management. This database should include

information about: (1) Business processes; (2) Systems and technology; (3) Policies and procedures; (4) Operational Risk; and (5) Risk mitigation.

Third, banks need to consider various internal and external factors in identifying and measuring operational risks, such as: (1) Internal factors include bank business processes, systems and technology, policies and procedures, and human resources. Banks must ensure that their business processes are efficient and effective, their systems and technology are secure and reliable, and their staff are trained and ready to handle situations that pose risks; (2) External factors include rules and regulations, economic and market conditions, and environmental factors. Banks should monitor changes in rules and regulations, economic and market conditions, and environmental factors to ensure that they are prepared to address risks that may arise; and (3) Banks must also consider specific risks related to their business, such as credit risk, market risk, operational risk and interest rate risk.

Fourth, there are 39 methods that Banks can use to identify and measure operational risks, including: (1) *Advanced Measurement Approach/AMA*; (2) *Analytical Hierarchy Process*; (3) *AS/NZS 3806-Compliance Management System for Reducing, Mitigating, Managing the Operational Risks*; (4) *AS/NZS 4360-Risk Management System*; (5) *AS/NZS 4444*; (6) *AS/NZS 4801-Occupational Health and Safety Management Systems*; (7) *AS/NZS 7799-Information Security Management*; (8) *Basic Indicator Approach/BIA*; (9) *Basel Committee on Banking Supervision*; (10) *Bayesian Theory*; (11) *Bow The Risk Assessment*; (12) *Enterprise Risk Management/ERM*; (13) *Failure Mode and Effect Analysis/FMEA*; (14) *Failure Modes and Effects and Critical Analysis/FMECA*; (15) *Fault Tree Analysis/FTA*; (16) *Fault Tree Analysis*; (17) *Fishbone Diagram*; (18) *Gaussian Mixture Model/GMM for Loss Distribution Approach*; (19) *Generalized Pareto*; (20) *Hazard Identification*; (21) *House of Risk/HOR Method*; (22) *Internal Control System*; (23) *ISO 14001 (Effective Environmental Management System*; (24) *ISO 31000:2018*; (25) *ISO 9001 (Quality Management System*; (26) *Kernel Density Estimation*; (27) *Loss Distribution Approach*; (28) *Mapping Assessment and Planning /MAP*; (29) *Multi-Attribute Failure Mode Analysis/MAFMA*; (30) *Pareta Diagram*; (31) *Payment Card Industry Data Security Standard/PCI-DSS*; (32) *Risk Breakdown Structure/RBS*; (33) *Risk Priority Number /RPN*; (34) *Risk Response Planning*; (35) *Standardized Approach/SA*; (36) *Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threat/SWOT*; (37) *Theory Acceptance Model/TAM*; (38) *Value of Potential Loss/OpVar*; (39) *Zakat Core Principles/ZCP*; (40) *Risk Control Self Assessment (RCSA)*; (41) *risk mapping*; (42) *Key Risk Indicators (KRI)*; (43) *Scorecards*; (46) *Event analysis*; and (47) *frequency matrix*.

Literature Review Study regarding Operational Risk Monitoring

There are 3 findings in the research topic surrounding operational risk monitoring in banking, namely:

First, banks must monitor operational risks in all their key activities that have potential risks. This includes activities such as financing, technical operations, and information management. This system should

ensure that banks always have up-to-date information about the risks they face and that they can make informed decisions based on that information.

Second, banks must carry out regular evaluations to ensure that they always understand the factors that cause operational risks and have the right strategies to overcome these risks.

Third, the process of monitoring and evaluating potential risks. The aim is to minimize the impact of losses that may arise and ensure consistency with the risk management plan. This process is carried out on an ongoing basis and is accompanied by regular reports that follow developments in operational risks and the effectiveness of risk control.

Literature Review Study regarding Operational Risk Control

There are 3 findings in the research topic in the context of operational risk control, namely:

First, banks must carry out risk supervision on an ongoing basis to ensure that operational risks can be accepted and managed well. Risk monitoring is carried out by taking steps to reduce, prevent or overcome risks. These actions can take the form of implementing new regulations and procedures, strengthening systems and infrastructure. With this, banks will be better prepared to face potential risks that may arise and can minimize negative impacts on the banking business.

Second, securing information technology systems is an important part of operational risk management in banking. Information technology systems play a key role in carrying out banking activities, so securing information technology systems is very important to minimize operational risks. Banks must also conduct regular penetration tests to ensure that information technology systems remain secure and have the ability to detect and overcome attacks. This helps banks understand the level of system vulnerabilities and take appropriate action to address them before an attack actually occurs. Securing information technology systems is a joint responsibility between banks and vendors who supply technology. Banks must ensure that the selected vendor has good security standards and complies with applicable regulations to ensure that the banking information technology system is safe and protected.

Third, banks must have a routine rotation system as part of efforts to manage operational risk. A regular rotation system helps reduce potential conflicts of interest and ensures that staff have a broad understanding of the bank's operations and risks. Regular rotation also helps ensure that staff have a deep understanding of existing internal control processes and systems, helping to reduce the possibility of irregularities or failures in internal controls. In addition, a regular rotation system also helps maintain the effectiveness and integrity of internal control by ensuring that staff have different and fresh perspectives on bank operations and risks. This also helps ensure that staff have updated knowledge of applicable regulations and industry standards.

Literature Review Study regarding Operational Risk Information Systems

There are 2 findings in the research topic surrounding Operational Risk Management Information Systems, namely

First, management information systems must be able to provide comprehensive and accurate reports to help organizations deal with deviations and risks effectively. Timely and accurate reports are critical because they help management and staff identify problems and make informed decisions. A comprehensive report should include information about the organization's performance, risks observed, and control actions taken. This should ensure that the organization has a clear view of operational conditions. Management information systems must also be able to automatically identify potential deviations and provide timely reports to ensure that preventive and corrective actions can be taken as quickly as possible. This helps ensure that organizations meet regulatory standards and ensure data and information security.

Second, banks must have a reporting mechanism for operational risks that provides information that meets user needs. This information includes aspects such as potential risks, effectiveness of risk controls, and changes in operational risk profiles. This reporting mechanism must meet applicable reporting standards and must be accepted by authorized parties such as internal and external supervisors. Effective and timely reporting is critical for banks as it helps them identify and understand their operational risks more deeply. This enables banks to make informed decisions and prioritize risk control measures accordingly. Reporting mechanisms must also comply with the principles of transparency and accountability. Banks must ensure that the reporting provided is accurate, reliable and easy to understand by users.

Literature Review Study regarding Determinants of Operational Risk

There are 34 research topics regarding the determinants of operational risk in banking, namely: (1) Agent-based modeling; (2) Board of Directors; (3) Business Combination; (5) Business Interruption; (6) Business Practices; (7) Customer; (8) Compensation; (9) Covid-19; (10) Collaboration System Risks; (11) Physical Asset Damage; (12) Digital Banking; (13) Economic Empowerment; (14) *Employees Fraud*; (15) *External Fraud*; (16) Islamic Execution, Delivery and Management; (17) company size; (18) *Good Corporate Governance /GCG*; (19) Human Resources; (20) Legal Risk; (21) *Internal Fraud*; (22) Income; (23) Information Management; (24) Internal Risk; (25) Investment Costs; (26) *Money Market Treasury Group*; (27) Operations; (29) Products; (30) Sales Process Risk; (31) Sharia Supervisory Board; (32) Social Entrepreneurship; (33) System Failure; (34) Technology Risk.

Literature Review Study regarding the Influence of Operational Risk

There are 10 research topics regarding the influence of operational risk in banking, namely:

(1) Financing. High operational risk can cause instability in the company's operational processes, such as disruption to internal systems or processes. This can result in a decrease in the confidence of stakeholders, including creditors and investors. As a result, companies

may experience difficulties in obtaining financing on favorable terms or even experience rejection of financing from external parties.

(2) *Financial Reports*. Uncontrolled operational risks can cause inaccuracies or defects in the financial reporting process. Failure to properly record transactions, poor implementation of internal controls, or data leaks can result in inaccurate information in financial reports. This can reduce the confidence of investors and other stakeholders in the company, and can cause legal and reputation problems.

(3) *Stock Market*. Companies with high operational risk tend to be less attractive to investors because of uncertainty in operational processes and financial reporting. As a result, the company's shares may experience selling pressure causing the share price to decline. On the other hand, if the company succeeds in managing operational risks well, investors may have more confidence and the company's shares may be more desirable on the stock market.

(4) *Non Performing Loans /NPL*. High operational risk in financial institutions, such as banks, can cause difficulties in managing their credit portfolio. If the credit granting process is inefficient or monitoring of credit quality is poor, then banks may face increased credit risk and more loans end up as NPLs.

(5) *Profit Growth*. Uncontrolled operational risks can lead to unexpected additional costs, such as recovery costs after system failures or legal costs resulting from regulatory violations. This can cause a decrease in the company's net profit.

(6) *Quality Cost Efficiency*. Operational risks that are not managed properly can hamper a company's cost efficiency because of the additional costs that must be borne to overcome operational problems. In addition, high operational risks can also affect the quality of a company's products or services, which can have a negative impact on brand image and customer satisfaction.

(7) *Reputation Level*. Bad operational risks can damage the reputation of a company or financial institution. Disruptions in service, legal violations, or data security issues can create negative perceptions among customers, investors, and the general public, which in turn can damage a company's image and reputation.

(8) *Return On Assets /ROA*. High operational risk can cause additional costs and potential losses, which in the end can reduce the company's ROA level. ROA measures the extent to which a company is able to generate profits from the assets it owns.

(9) *Return On Equity /ROE*. ROE can be influenced by the company's net profit level. Uncontrolled operational risks can cause a decrease in net income, and therefore, can reduce ROE, which is a measure of the rate of return for shareholders.

(10) *Stock Returns*. Company stock performance tends to be influenced by various factors, including operational risk. If a company manages operational risks well, this can increase investor confidence and can contribute to better stock performance.

Literature Review Study regarding Operational Risk Mitigation

There are 9 research topics regarding operational risk mitigation in banking, namely:

(1) *Asset Liability Management/ALMA*. The procedure is as follows: Identify risks associated with the timing of financial assets and liabilities, diversify the portfolio of assets and liabilities to reduce concentration risk, and use financial instruments such as derivatives to protect against market fluctuations.

(2) *Failure Mode and Effect Analysis/FMEA*. The procedure is as follows: Identify potential failures in operational processes, assess the impact of each identified failure, and develop preventive or corrective actions to reduce the risk of failure and its impact.

(3) *Internal Auditing*. The procedure is as follows: Assess the effectiveness of existing internal controls, identify areas that are vulnerable to operational risks, and provide recommendations for improvements or process changes to reduce risks.

(4) *Linkage Program*. The procedure is as follows: Establish coordination between various units in the organization, share information and experience related to operational risks, and develop joint strategies to overcome risks that involve many departments.

(5) *Operational Risk Management/ORM*. The procedure is as follows: Identification of operational risks relevant to the business process, assessment of the impact and likelihood of the risk occurring, and development and implementation of appropriate controls and mitigation measures.

(6) Risk Retention. The procedure is as follows: Have sufficient funds to handle the impact of risks if they occur and determine the maximum risk limit that can be borne.

(7) Risk reduction. The procedures are as follows: Strengthen operational process controls and conduct training to increase awareness and compliance with operational policies and procedures.

(8) Risk Transfer. Risk transfer is a way to transfer operational risks to third parties, such as insurance. In this case, the company pays a premium to get protection if the risk occurs.

(9) Risk Avoidance. Risk avoidance means an organization avoids activities or processes that have the potential to create operational risks that cannot be managed or overcome properly. This step may be taken if the risk is too high or intolerable.

Conclusion, Discussion, and Research Limitations

The conclusions are as follows: (1) The number of research publications on operational risk in the Sharia and Conventional Financial Industry from 2002 to 2022 has increased significantly from year to year. Total publications reached 348 research journals, with 186 journals indexed by Scopus and 162 journals indexed by Sinta. (2) Through visualization using VOSviewer, research on operational risks in the Sharia and Conventional Finance Industry is divided into 9 clusters with a different number of topics in each cluster. (3) Based on the *literature review* study, 11 main themes of research on operational risk in the Sharia and Conventional Finance Industry were identified, including the definition

and objectives of operational risk, risk monitoring, strategy, risk levels, risk policies and procedures, risk identification and measurement, risk monitoring, risk control, risk information systems, risk determinants, risk influences, and risk mitigation.

This research discussion is to outline topics that are usually studied by researchers, so that they can find research gaps and become a reference for future researchers.

The limitation of this research is the use of a smaller data sample, both from national accredited journals Sinta and international journals indexed by Scopus to interpret a broader research scheme. can obtain the following search results: *First*, the mapping results are expected to show a higher and broader degree of generalization. *Second*, the results of the literature review can be interpreted in a more complex way.

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